

THE PSYCHE OF THE LYRICAL HERO IN AYDIN HAJIYEVA'S POETRY

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Abstract. The article presents the work of the talented poetess Aydin Hojiyeva from the point of view of lyrical heroine and poetic experience. The nature of the lyrical protagonist's thinking and the features of his artistic interpretation are revealed. The various situations and contradictions expressed in the spiritual world of the lyrical hero are analyzed. Aydin Khodzhiyeva's lyrical imagery and poetic imagery are highlighted.

Keywords: lyrical hero, social reality, real image, extraordinary image, lyrical experience, poetic image, lyrical process.

ПСИХИКА ЛИРИЧЕСКОГО ГЕРОЯ В ПОЭЗИИ АЙДЫН ГАДЖИЕВОЙ

Аннотация. В статье представлено творчество талантливой поэтессы Айдын Ходжиевой с точки зрения лирической героини и поэтического опыта. Раскрывается характер мышления лирического героя и особенности его художественной интерпретации. Анализируются различные ситуации и противоречия, выраженные в духовном мире лирического героя. Выделены лирические образы и поэтические образы Айдын Ходжиевой.

Ключевые слова: лирический герой, социальная реальность, реальный образ, необычный образ, лирический опыт, поэтический образ, лирический процесс.

INTRODUCTION

In modern Uzbek literature, lyrical works rank high both in terms of weight and quality. Because a person cannot easily express his inner feelings in normal relationships. And a talented person transfers the experiences that are "folded" in the human heart before coming out to his lyrical hero. "A lyrical hero is a human figure in a lyrical work, a bearer of lyrical experiences. As any image, the lyrical hero not only exhibits unique, unique individual personality qualities, but also has certain generalizing universal characteristics, which requires him not to be considered the same as the poet's personality.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The talented poetess Aydin Hajiyeva captivates the poet through her lyrical hero. Because in the poetry of the poetess, both pain and joy are inextricably linked. In the work of Aydin Hajiyeva, it is common to approach natural phenomena and scenes of life from different angles. The artist looks at reality with an artistic eye, finds a symbol in it, and creates beautiful images.

The mountains know that I will find you
He said: "He is calm and quiet like us."
Hot flashes that haven't caught fire yet
He said: "He is bright and cheerful like us."

Anyone familiar with the lyrics of the generation of the 80s will immediately realize that such poems are not unfamiliar to us. In the poetry of Aydin Hajiyeva and her comrades, attention is strongly drawn to the unexpected situations of life and human existence. The lyrical hero of this generation has an unusual, unfamiliar worldview, and if you read it carefully, you can always feel the spirit of protest. A lyrical hero wants to do good, to grow and mature hour by hour, minute by minute. But it is difficult to compare with "richness" and "quiet mountains".

Aydin Hajiyeva portrays her lyrical hero based on various images. The poet looks at an object with many eyes. "Lightning" and "mountains" do not fall from the peak they occupy, mountains are the abode of height and glory. The lyrical hero loves everyone, wants to see his loved ones in high places. And the peaks are always cold and lifeless. In her poems, the poet pays more attention to the expressiveness and unexpectedness of the expression than to the realistic depiction of social reality.

The trees whispered on my way:

"The roots of love are as strong as ours!"

A double dove flew in my head:

"Love as soft as my feathers".

The lucky and happy moments of the lyrical hero were not so many. It was the feeling of love that threw him into the embrace of unfaithful sorrow and filled him with happiness. For the poetess, nothing but love is fleeting and temporary, and the "trees" try to remind the lyrical character of her feelings. As the "roots of love" are deeply embedded in the heart, the pains of the heart become bigger and bigger. Extraordinary images in Aydin Hajiyeva's poems awaken the lyrical hero. Comparison of love to "double doves' feathers" puts the poet in a gentle mood due to the external soft tone of the poem.

"...often the lyrical hero is very close to the poet's personality in relation to his nature, people and life events, but they almost never completely merge." Aydin Hajiyeva also infuses some aspects of her personality into her lyrical hero. By the middle of the 80s, the spring weather began in the garden of poetry. New buds of poetry began to write leaves:

I found the heart of spring,

The flowers were blooming.

I kissed the triumphal dress of autumn,

I picked leaves in the garden.

In this poem "Opportunity Says", we observe that the lyrical hero created by the poetess finds its reflection through the poetess "I". His inner world is interpreted in various ways in one way or another. The poet makes friends with spring. For him, spring will be the sight of life and the support of his heart. The lyrical hero of the poem first of all wants to share his joy and pain with her, and every time spring comes, he seems to return to the innocent world of youth.

RESULTS

Usually, Aydin Hajiyeva synthesizes her mental and psychological state. The series of subtle feelings that have struck a chord in the artist's perception reaches its climax in the experiences of the lyrical hero. A poetic character is fully formed in it. Accordingly, the facets of human thinking are continuously combined in the lyrical process.

I am happy, I am happy

I am not on earth, but in the heavens!

I'm as real as legendary girls

I am in epics where love is over.

"Personal pride, stubbornness, at the same time, incomparable hard work, defiance, incomparable strong memory, the instinct of constant study, honesty determine the uniqueness of the poet's work." Aydin Hajiyeva abandons the quiet, brooding, closed mind, on the contrary, the lyrical hero is now open, violent, and able to control his emotions. The poet is surprised by the fact that the poet speaks about happiness and a happy life. Because it seems that happiness is not

yet perfect. He knows the value of his poems, expresses the experiences of a creator who is satisfied with the perfection of lyrical lines and proud of his spiritual maturity.

Pain and suffering of loneliness
If it falls to the top of the mountain,
The sunset sun of my joy
He found life in your eyes.

The feeling of loneliness that deeply scratches the heart of the lyrical hero throws the poet's heart into this vortex of feeling. Fatal blows from the mountain "set the sun of joy" of the lyrical hero. But all this is temporary. The morning dawns again and brings peace to the soul. The lyrical "I" makes the sun a partner in its worries and joys. He finds it, and now the sun is with him.

DISCUSSION

Even so, the soul is disturbed again:

I know - the light of your soul
Sadness casts a shadow on my face.
The light will not fit in your sky
Let me tell you my joy!

Happiness is sweet. The light will wake up in the heart again. Lucky you... The poet's wish becomes a poem. And wishes move to the moment. And then it gets longer and longer. And the poet is tired of telling the tale of joy that reaches far away. Because the poet is interested in hopeful moments.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, in the work of Aydin Hajiyeva, the lyrical hero is interpreted through the "me" of the poetess. When it comes to various situations, conflicts expressed in the spiritual world of the lyrical hero, and in general about the personality of the poetess, unusual scenes are often found in Aydin Hajiyeva's lyrics. At the same time, the worldview of the lyrical hero in the poetess's poetry is strongly influenced by social reality, and the spirit of the era is instilled.

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